

An absorption spectral analysis of 4f-4f transitions to explore the comparison of energy interaction parameters and electric dipole intensity parameters for the complexation of Pr^{III} with D-proline and DL-proline

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Abstract : Comparative absorption spectra involving 4f-4f transitions on Pr^{III} complex with D-proline and DL-proline have been carried out in CH₃OH, CH₃CN, DMF and dioxane as well as in their equimolar mixtures. Both energy interaction and intensity parameters have been calculated using partial and multiple regression method to explore the effect of small chemical and structural difference due to ligands and solvents on significant variation in the intensities of observed 4f-4f absorption bands.

Keywords : Proline, hypersensitive, pseudo-hypersensitive, oscillator strength, Judd-Ofelt parameter.

Introduction

The absorption spectra of lanthanides involving 4f-4f transitions have been studied by various workers in probing biochemical reactions involving paramagnetic Ln^{III} in solution. This unique feature of lanthanide in biochemical research lies in its ability to replace Ca^{II} in specific isomorphous manner, due to close resemblance between Ln^{III} and Ca^{II} in ionic size, donor atom preference, bonding and coordination characteristics¹. Shah *et al.*² studied comparative 4f-4f transition spectra of Pr^{III} with lysozyme by using energy interaction parameters to explain the behaviour of binding between them.

Ketzin³ applied the ability of paramagnetic Ln^{III} as absorption difference probe in studies of sugar acids and amino acids as ligands. The hypersensitive band of lanthanides gave largest intensification when carboxylic group entered into the coordination sphere of lanthanide. Quantitative influence varied considerably with certain details of the structure of the anions. Difference absorption spectra of Ln^{III} trypsinase and bovine serum albuminate have identical shape to those recorded for amino acids, yet there were major changes in the intensities of the 4f-4f bands, specially the hypersensitive band^{4,5}.

The present investigation studied the sensitivity of pseudo-hypersensitive transitions through the calculation of Slater-Condon parameter (F_k), Nephelauxetic ratio (β), Racah (E^k), Lande parameter (ξ_{4f}), bonding para-

meter ($b^{1/2}$) and percent covalency (δ) as well as oscillator strength (P) and Judd-Ofelt parameters T_λ ($\lambda = 2, 4, 6$) to discuss the ligand's varying nature of coordination towards the metal ion. The ligand used in the present study are the structurally related D-proline and DL-proline containing both nitrogen and oxygen donor atoms. Proline⁶ (pyrrolidine-2-carboxylic acid) is the only heterocyclic amino acid among twenty amino acids used in living organisms as the building blocks of proteins. It is an imino acid as it contains no amino group, nonetheless, it is an amino acid. Proline is found in essentially most proteins and is a major constituents in collagens, the fibrous protein of connective tissue. Proline plays the important role to determine the proteins structural shape when amino acids are incorporated into them. Proline containing one asymmetric carbon atom can exist in three forms, D-proline, L-proline and DL-proline (\pm). D-proline and L-proline are the mirror image of each other known as enantiomers. DL-Proline is the equimolar mixture of D- and L-proline. The only difference is that DL-form is optically inactive while the other two forms are optically active. L-Form represent the natural type found in living plants and animal tissues. The L-form is used in human protein structures and is more compatible to human biochemistry than the D-form. The DL-proline is synonymous of proline.

Experimental

Praseodymium nitrate of 99% purity obtained from CDH Analytical Reagent and D- and DL-proline from Acrose company are used for spectral analysis. The solvent used are DMF, CH₃OH, CH₃CN and dioxane of AR grade from qualigents.

The saturated solutions of praseodymium nitrate, D-proline and DL-proline are prepared in different solvents. All solutions are prepared in 10⁻² M concentration. The complexes have been made in the molar ratio 1 : 1. The absorption spectra of the complexes are recorded on Perkin-Elmer-Lambda-35 UV-Vis spectrophotometer upgraded with high resolution and expansion of scale in the region 350–900 nm at 298 K.

Results and discussion

The transitions involving 4*f*-4*f* transitions are very sensitive towards immediate coordination environment around Ln^{III} ion. The calculation of band intensity of such transitions is based on the theoretical treatment developed by Judd⁷ and Ofelt⁸. They consider the transitions are essentially electric dipole in character and the oscillator strength corresponding to induced dipole transition $\psi_j \rightarrow \psi_j'$ as given by

$$P_{cal} = \sum_{\lambda=2,4,6} T_{\lambda} \nu (f^n \psi_j || U^{\lambda} || f^n \psi_j')^2 \quad (1)$$

where U^{λ} is the matrix element of unit tensor operator connecting initial $\langle f^n \psi_j |$ and final $| f^n \psi_j' \rangle$ through three phenomenological parameters T_{λ} ($\lambda = 2, 4, 6$) called Judd-Ofelt parameters. These parameters are related to the radial wave function of the states and ligand field parameters that characterize the surrounding field. The transition levels and the matrix elements used for the intensity analysis of Pr^{III} complexes is given by Carnall *et al.*⁹ in Table 1.

Table 1. Transition energies and intraconfigurational $U^{(\lambda)}$ matrix elements for Pr^{III}

Levels	Aproximate ν (cm ⁻¹)	$[U^{(2)}]^2$	$[U^{(4)}]^2$	$[U^{(6)}]^2$
¹ D ₂	16780	0.0026	0.0170	0.0520
³ P ₀	20770	0	0.1728	0
³ P ₁	21360	0	0.1707	0
³ P ₂	22500	0	0.0362	0.1355

All transitions originate from ³H₄ ground multiplet.

The measured intensity of an absorption band is related to the probability (P) for the absorption of radiant energy (oscillator strength) by the expression

$$P = 4.318 \times 10^{-9} \int \epsilon(\nu) d\nu \quad (2)$$

where ϵ is the molar extinction coefficient corresponding to energy ν (cm⁻¹) and other symbols have their usual meaning. From these, the values of Judd-Ofelt parameters T_2, T_4, T_6 are calculated by partial and multiple regression method using the Judd-Ofelt expressions

$$\frac{P_{obs}}{\nu} = [(U^2)]^2 T_2 + [(U^4)]^4 T_4 + [(U^6)]^2 T_6 \quad (3)$$

In the electronic transition of 4*f*-4*f*, the electrostatic term E_0 is expressed in terms of the product of Slater radial integral known as Slater-Condon^{10,11} parameter F_k and is given by

$$E = \sum_{K=0}^{K=6} K^k F_K = \sum_{K=0}^{K=6} f_k F^k \quad (4)$$

where K_k is the angular coefficient.

The Slater-Condon parameters known as direct integral and necessary a positive and decreasing function of K are given by

$$F_1^k = \int_0^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{r_{<}^k}{r_{>}^{k+1}} R_i^2(r_i) R_j^2(r_j) r_i^2 r_j^2 dr_i dr_j \quad (5)$$

where R is the 4*f* radial wave function; $r_{<}$ and $r_{>}$ are the radii of near and more distant electrons, and i and j are the i -th and j -th electrons under consideration. Condon and Shortly¹¹ redefined F_K integrals in terms of reduced integral F^k related to each other as

$$F_k = \frac{F^k}{D^k} \quad (6)$$

Combining (5) and (6) the reduced Slater integral can be written as

$$F_k = \frac{1}{D_k} \int_0^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{r_{<}^k}{r_{>}^{k+1}} R_i^2(r_i) R_j^2(r_j) r_i^2 r_j^2 dr_i dr_j \quad (7)$$

where D_k is the denominator and F_k are coefficient of linear combination and represent the angular part of integration, F_k expectation value of scalar product ($C_1^{(k)} C_2^{(k)}$).

Racah energy parameters E^k 's are given by linear combination of F_k (8)¹² as

$$E^1 = \frac{70F_2 + 231F_4 + 20.02F_6}{9}$$

$$E^2 = \frac{F_2 - 3F_4 + 7F_6}{9}$$

$$E^3 = \frac{5F_2 + 6F_4 - 9F_6}{3} \quad (8)$$

The energy, E_{so} arising from the most important magnetic interaction which are spin-orbit interaction may be written as

$$E_{so} = A_{so}\xi_{4f} \quad (9)$$

where A_{so} is the angular part of spin orbit interaction and ξ_{4f} is the radial integral known as Land's parameter. By first order approximation the energy E_j of the j -th level is given by Wong¹³ as

$$E_j(F_k, \xi_{4f}) = E_{0j}(F_k^0, \xi_{4f}^0) + \frac{\partial E_j}{\partial F_k} \cdot \Delta F_k + \frac{\partial E_j}{\partial \xi_{4f}} \cdot \Delta \xi_{4f} \quad (10)$$

where E_{0j} is the zero order energy of the j -th level.

The value of F_k and ξ_{4f} are given by

$$F_k = F_k^0 + \Delta F_k \text{ and } \xi_{4f} = \xi_{4f}^0 + \Delta \xi_{4f} \quad (11)$$

The difference between the observed E_j value and the zero order value, ΔE_j is evaluated by

$$\Delta E_j = \sum_{k=2,4,6} \frac{\partial E_j}{\partial F_k} \Delta F_k + \frac{\partial E_j}{\partial \xi_{4f}} \Delta \xi_{4f} \quad (12)$$

By using the zero order energy and partial derivatives of Pr^{III} given by Wong¹³, the above equation can be solved by least square technique and the value of ΔF_k and $\Delta \xi_{4f}$ can be found out. From these values, the value of F_2 , F_4 , F_6 and ξ_{4f} are found out by using eq. (11).

Nephelauxetic effect, the measure of covalency¹⁴⁻¹⁶ can be expressed in terms of Slatore-Condon and Racah parameters of the free ion and complex ion^{11,17-19}

$$\beta = \frac{F_K^C}{F_K^f} \text{ or } \beta = \frac{E_C^K}{E_F^K} \quad (13)$$

The amount of mixing of $4f$ orbital and ligand represented by bonding parameter ($b^{1/2}$) is related to Nephelauxetic effect as

$$b^{1/2} = \left[\frac{1-\beta}{2} \right]^{1/2} \quad (14)$$

Sinha¹⁸ defined the percent covalency parameter as δ

$$\delta = \frac{1-\beta}{\beta} \times 100 \quad (15)$$

The intensities of induced electric dipole transitions of lanthanide ions are almost independent of the environment and dipole strength of a particular electric dipole transition of a lanthanide in different matrices varies by a factor less than two or three. However, a few transitions are very sensitive to the environment and these are usually more intense in lanthanide complexes than for uncomplexed ions in aqueous solution. Jorgensen and Judd called these transition as hypersensitive transition obeying the selection rules for quadrupole transition¹⁴

$$|\Delta J| \leq 2, |\Delta L| \leq 2 \text{ and } \Delta S = 0$$

For $Pr^{III} \ ^3H_4 \rightarrow \ ^3F_2$ transition occurring around 5200 cm^{-1} is the hypersensitive. However, the transitions $\ ^3H_4 \rightarrow \ ^3P_2$, $\ ^3H_4 \rightarrow \ ^3P_1$, $\ ^3H_4 \rightarrow \ ^3P_0$ and $\ ^3H_4 \rightarrow \ ^1D_2$ have been found to exhibit high sensitivity towards even minor changes in the immediate coordination environment around Pr^{III} ^{20,21} though these transitions cannot be regarded as hypersensitive as they do not obey the selection rules, yet these show substantial intensification on complexation of metal ion and yield wide variation of oscillator strength and thus prompted us to coin the term 'Ligand Mediated Pseudo-hypersensitive Transitions'.

The various energy parameters F_k ($k = 2, 4, 6$) i.e. Slatore-Condon parameter, β Nephelauxetic ratio, Racah E^k , ξ_{4f} and $b^{1/2}$ (the extent of covalency around the metal ion in the solution) have been reported in Table 2, which shows fair agreement with the theory involved in Pr^{III} complex. The decrease in the parametric values of F_k , E^k , ξ_{4f} , the decrease in the inter-electronic repulsion and spin-orbit interaction which suggest that expansion of the central metal ion take place upon complexation leading to red shift in most of the absorption bands from free ions and in accordance with the theory of $f-f$ transitions reported earlier^{22,23}.

The values of Nephelauxetic ratio β and bonding parameter $b^{1/2}$ indicate some extent of covalent bonding in Pr^{III} complex ion. The small value of $b^{1/2}$ and little variation in it suggest that $4f$ orbitals are very slightly involved in the bonding with ligands.

The intensities of the observed bands have been measured in terms of oscillator strength ($P \times 10^6$). The ex-

Table 2. Computed values of energy interaction Slater-Condon (F_k) (cm^{-1}), spin-orbit interaction (ξ_{4f}) (cm^{-1}), Racah parameters (E^k) (cm^{-1}), Nephelauxetic ratio (β), bonding parameter ($b^{1/2}$) and covalency percentage (δ) of Pr^{III} ; Pr^{III} : D-proline (1 : 1); Pr^{III} : DL-proline (1 : 1) in aqueous and aquated organic solvents and their equimolar mixtures

System	F_2	F_4	F_6	ξ_{4f}	E^1	E^2	E^3	β	$b^{1/2}$	δ
(1) Solvent-water :										
Pr^{III}	309.27	42.69	4.67	722.59	3511.71	23.76	586.84	0.947	0.1627	5.5933
Pr^{III} : D-proline	309.5	42.72	4.67	722.9	3514	23.78	587.27	0.9476	0.1619	5.5322
Pr^{III} : DL-proline	309.43	42.71	4.67	722.27	3513.55	23.77	587.14	0.9471	0.1627	5.5909
(2) Solvent- CH_3OH :										
Pr^{III}	309.28	42.69	4.67	721.5	3511.81	23.76	586.85	0.9463	0.1639	5.6751
Pr^{III} : D-proline	309.13	42.67	4.66	720.32	3510.15	23.75	586.57	0.9453	0.1654	5.7896
Pr^{III} : DL-proline	309.28	42.69	4.67	721.45	3511.8	23.76	586.85	0.9463	0.1639	5.679
(3) Solvent-DMF :										
Pr^{III}	309.27	42.69	4.67	722.34	3511.7	23.76	586.83	0.9469	0.163	5.6121
Pr^{III} : D-proline	309.28	42.69	4.67	722.58	3511.84	23.76	586.86	0.947	0.1627	5.5919
Pr^{III} : DL-proline	309.00	42.65	4.66	720.02	3508.63	23.74	586.32	0.9449	0.1660	5.8337
(4) Solvent- CH_3CN :										
Pr^{III}	309.47	42.72	4.67	722	3514.02	23.78	587.22	0.9469	0.1629	5.6049
Pr^{III} : D-proline	309.43	42.71	4.67	721.68	3513.47	23.77	587.13	0.9466	0.1633	5.6071
Pr^{III} : DL-proline	309.47	42.722	4.67	721.99	3513.94	23.77	587.21	0.9469	0.1629	5.6072
(5) Solvent-dioxane :										
Pr^{III}	309.27	42.69	4.67	722.34	3511.7	23.76	586.83	0.9469	0.163	5.6121
Pr^{III} : D-proline	309.28	42.69	4.67	722.58	3511.84	23.76	586.86	0.947	0.1627	5.5119
Pr^{III} : DL-proline	309.22	42.68	4.66	721.87	3511.13	23.76	586.74	0.9465	0.1636	5.6566
(6) Solvent-DMF + dioxane :										
Pr^{III}	309.06	42.66	4.66	720.48	3509.29	23.74	586.43	0.9453	0.1654	5.7895
Pr^{III} : D-proline	309.07	42.66	4.66	720.85	3509.47	23.74	586.46	0.9456	0.165	5.7582
Pr^{III} : DL-proline	309.04	42.66	4.66	720.27	3509.05	23.74	586.39	0.9451	0.1657	5.809
(7) Solvent- CH_3OH + CH_3CN :										
Pr^{III}	309.34	42.7	4.67	721.99	3512.47	23.76	586.96	0.9467	0.1632	5.628
Pr^{III} : D-proline	309.54	42.72	4.67	722.44	3512.54	23.77	586.97	0.947	0.1627	5.593
Pr^{III} : DL-proline	309.24	42.69	4.66	721.73	3511.33	23.76	586.77	0.9464	0.1637	5.6643
(8) Solvent- CH_3OH + DMF :										
Pr^{III}	309.13	42.67	4.66	720.32	3510.15	23.75	586.57	0.9453	0.1654	5.7896
Pr^{III} : D-proline	309.11	42.67	4.66	720.21	3509.85	23.75	586.53	0.9452	0.1656	5.8021
Pr^{III} : DL-proline	309.13	42.67	4.66	720.5	3510.12	23.75	586.57	0.9454	0.1652	5.7759
(9) Solvent- CH_3OH + dioxane :										
Pr^{III}	309.3	42.69	4.67	722.26	3512.05	23.76	586.89	0.9468	0.163	5.6135
Pr^{III} : D-proline	309.24	42.69	4.66	721.58	3511.4	23.76	586.78	0.9463	0.1639	5.675
Pr^{III} : DL-proline	309.24	42.69	4.66	721.73	3511.33	23.76	586.77	0.9464	0.1637	5.6643
(10) Solvent-DMF + CH_3CN :										
Pr^{III}	309.07	42.66	4.66	720.26	3509.39	23.74	586.45	0.9451	0.1656	5.8045
Pr^{III} : D-proline	309.04	42.66	4.66	720.06	3509.1	23.74	586.4	0.945	0.1659	5.8241
Pr^{III} : DL-proline	309.04	42.66	4.66	720.27	3509.05	23.74	586.39	0.9451	0.1657	5.809
(11) Solvent- CH_3CN + dioxane :										
Pr^{III}	309.33	42.7	4.67	723.14	3512.33	23.76	586.94	0.9475	0.162	5.5419
Pr^{III} : D-proline	309.21	42.68	4.66	721.62	3510.99	23.75	586.71	0.9463	0.1639	5.6777
Pr^{III} : DL-proline	309.21	42.68	4.66	721.72	3511.03	23.75	586.72	0.9463	0.1638	5.6696

Table 3. Experimental and computed values of oscillatory strength ($P \times 10^6$) and Judd-Ofelt ($T \times 10^{10}$) parameters for Pr^{III} , Pr^{III} : D-proline (1 : 1) and Pr^{III} : DL-proline (1 : 1) in aqueous and aqated organic solvents and their equimolar mixtures

System	${}^3H_4 \rightarrow {}^1D_2$		${}^3H_4 \rightarrow {}^3P_0$		${}^3H_4 \rightarrow {}^3P_1$		${}^3H_4 \rightarrow {}^3P_2$		T_2	T_4	T_6
	P_{obs}	P_{cal}	P_{obs}	P_{cal}	P_{obs}	P_{cal}	P_{obs}	P_{cal}			
(1) Solvent-water :											
Pr^{III}	0.7390	0.739	0.9054	0.3570	0.8826	0.5647	3.6924	3.6924	-77.632	2.523	11.423
Pr^{III} : D-proline	1.0131	1.0131	0.8402	0.5474	0.8533	1.1507	3.6009	3.6009	-9.534	2.341	11.172
Pr^{III} : DL-proline	1.0894	1.0894	0.8826	0.5647	0.8963	1.1292	3.7298	3.7298	-0.582	2.459	11.563
(2) Solvent-DMF :											
Pr^{III}	1.3044	1.3044	0.9589	0.7103	0.9733	1.2256	4.2912	4.2912	11.633	2.675	13.371
Pr^{III} : D-proline	1.1984	1.1984	0.9419	0.6884	0.9560	1.2133	4.2703	4.2703	-10.997	2.627	13.314
Pr^{III} : DL-proline	1.0985	1.0985	0.9625	0.7157	0.9769	1.2274	2.0481	2.0481	111.97	2.285	6.005
(3) Solvent- CH_3OH :											
Pr^{III}	0.9926	0.9926	0.8102	0.5363	0.8227	1.1008	3.4328	3.4328	-2.4898	2.258	10.646
Pr^{III} : D-proline	0.4599	0.4599	0.7710	0.5012	0.7828	1.0567	3.4104	3.4104	-121.88	2.148	10.599
Pr^{III} : DL-proline	0.9910	0.9910	0.8132	0.7093	0.8258	1.0944	3.5836	3.536	-12.729	2.267	11.138
(4) Solvent- CH_3CN :											
Pr^{III}	1.0210	1.0210	0.8368	0.5492	0.8513	1.1448	3.4967	3.4967	-0.332	2.332	10.822
Pr^{III} : D-proline	1.1067	1.1067	0.8382	0.5462	0.8499	1.1450	3.4941	3.4941	19.063	2.335	10.83
Pr^{III} : DL-proline	2.1907	2.1907	0.8257	0.5358	0.8386	1.1331	3.5268	3.5268	262.62	2.3	10.938
(5) Solvent-dioxane :											
Pr^{III}	1.0576	1.0376	0.7554	0.4632	0.7672	1.0640	3.6771	3.6771	-3.783	2.106	11.487
Pr^{III} : D-proline	1.0407	1.0407	0.7636	0.5011	0.7752	1.0417	3.4519	3.4519	7.039	2.128	10.743
Pr^{III} : DL-proline	1.1179	1.1179	1.0211	0.5317	1.0373	1.5345	3.5844	3.5844	15.302	2.847	10.986
(6) Solvent-DMF + dioxane :											
Pr^{III}	1.3154	1.3154	0.9551	0.7036	0.9697	1.2251	4.3416	4.3416	10.757	2.664	13.532
Pr^{III} : D-proline	1.2893	1.2893	0.8853	0.6151	0.8988	1.1731	4.3653	4.3653	3.353	2.469	13.662
Pr^{III} : DL-proline	1.2200	1.2200	0.9157	0.6883	0.9298	1.1607	3.8109	3.8109	-6.333	2.554	13.378
(7) Solvent- CH_3OH + DMF :											
Pr^{III}	1.3429	1.3429	1.0787	0.7069	1.0950	1.4725	4.3248	4.3248	17.894	3.008	13.378
Pr^{III} : D-proline	1.3715	1.3715	0.9584	0.6914	0.9729	1.2439	4.2517	4.2517	29.631	2.672	13.229
Pr^{III} : DL-proline	0.9910	0.9910	0.8132	0.5487	0.8258	1.0944	3.5836	3.5836	-12.729	2.267	11.138
(8) Solvent-DMF + CH_3CN :											
Pr^{III}	1.0465	1.0465	0.8328	0.6419	0.8454	1.0392	4.1060	4.1060	-34.391	2.323	12.851
Pr^{III} : D-proline	1.1247	1.1247	0.9376	0.6783	0.9518	1.2150	4.3954	4.3954	-4.119	2.615	13.724
Pr^{III} : DL-proline	1.2973	1.2973	0.9389	0.6891	0.9531	1.2067	4.0800	4.0800	23.924	2.618	12.689
(9) Solvent- CH_3OH + dioxane :											
Pr^{III}	1.0676	1.0676	0.8547	0.8289	0.9654	1.0891	3.5574	3.5574	5.6274	2.65	10.949
Pr^{III} : D-proline	1.0869	1.0869	0.7954	0.5275	0.8077	1.0798	3.5924	3.5924	8.193	2.217	11.181
Pr^{III} : DL-proline	1.1400	1.1400	0.8339	0.5433	0.8465	1.1415	3.7045	3.7045	13.022	2.325	11.528
(10) Solvent- CH_3CN + dioxane :											
Pr^{III}	0.8230	0.8230	0.8309	0.5240	0.8440	1.1558	3.7143	3.7143	-59.912	2.317	11.553
Pr^{III} : D-proline	1.2101	1.2101	0.8895	0.5400	0.9035	1.2585	3.6179	3.6179	34.494	2.48	11.196
Pr^{III} : DL-proline	1.0545	1.0545	0.8132	0.5487	0.8258	1.0944	3.5835	3.5835	1.685	2.267	11.137
(11) Solvent-MeOH + CH_3CN :											
Pr^{III}	0.9997	0.9997	0.7433	0.5136	0.4503	0.3789	3.5214	3.5214	-5.548	1.236	11.207
Pr^{III} : D-proline	1.0422	1.0422	0.7676	0.5158	0.7796	1.0353	3.4334	3.4334	8.577	2.14	10.678
Pr^{III} : DL-proline	0.9331	0.9331	0.7275	0.5130	0.7389	0.9568	3.4648	3.4648	-17.769	2.028	10.81

perimental and calculated values of oscillator strength and Judd-Ofelt have been given in Table 3. The values of oscillator strengths both experimental and computed match effectively for ${}^3H_4 \rightarrow {}^3P_2$ and ${}^3H_4 \rightarrow {}^1D_2$ while we observed some overestimated values for ${}^3H_4 \rightarrow {}^3P_0$ transition²⁴⁻²⁶.

Generally, the variation of T_λ parameters is directly reflected in the relative magnitude of the oscillator strengths of different 4*f*-4*f* transitions. T_2 occasionally show negative values and hence becomes meaningless. This is because only ${}^3F_2 \leftarrow {}^3H_4$ transition occurring around 5200 cm^{-1} has a significant $U^{(2)}$ matrix element but it is generally not included in the data set of Pr^{III} complexes especially in solution²⁷⁻²⁹. Comparative absorption spectra of Pr^{III} -proline in DMF : water (50 : 50) showing the mode of coordination affect the energy interaction parameters and oscillator strength of the pseudo-hypersensitive transitions is shown in Fig. 1.

energy interaction parameters, spectral intensities and consequently the Judd-Ofelt parameters reflecting the varying behaviour of coordination around Pr^{III}

Comparative absorption spectra of Pr^{III} : D-proline in different solvents showing the affinities of solvents towards Pr^{III} is shown in Fig. 2. The difference in the spectral pattern, oscillator strengths and intensity parameters of energy bands shows varying coordination powers of solvents suggesting the difference in relative sensitivity of 4*f*-4*f* transitions towards the coordination changes brought about by the nature of solvent. Solvents induced intensification of absorption bands, DMF being induced maximum intensification followed by solvent mixtures having DMF as one of the components.

Conclusion :

From the above discussion it can be concluded that D- and DL-proline are expected to form inner sphere com-

Fig. 1. Comparative absorption spectra of (a) Pr^{III} , (b) Pr^{III} : D-proline, (c) Pr^{III} : DL-proline in DMF

The proline ligands show same affinities towards Pr^{III} . Although both D- and DL-proline have almost same properties in all aspects, we observed substantial changes in

plexes around the metal ion. The proton from the carboxylic group migrates towards the amino group and oxygen of the carboxylate group links to the metal ion.

Fig. 2. Comparative absorption spectra of Pr^{III} : D-proline in (a) DMF, (b) CH₃CN, (c) dioxane and (d) CH₃OH.

The classical zwitterions resonance form of the acid is promoted by the highly charged lanthanide ion. This in fact contributes a significant amount of electron-density to the lanthanides. This might be one of the reasons why low intensities of bands are observed.

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